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**Concession Patterns and Strategies in Language Acquisition Results &
Discussion Discourse: A Corpus-Linguistics Study**

Umar Waqar Azim

Lecturer, Iqra University, Islamabad Campus

Phd Linguistics Scholar, Air University, Islamabad

Dr. Humera Faraz

Assistant Professor, Air University Islamabad

Abstract

Concessive markers such as *although*, *despite*, *however*, and *while* are paramount in academic writing for signaling contrast and tempering claims within a systemic-functional approach (Halliday & Hasan, 1976; Biber & Gray, 2010). Studies on the use of these markers in the Second Language Acquisition (SLA) texts appear to have received little attention from a corpus linguistics perspective. Informed by SFL and the framework provided by Zhang (2021), this study works with a corpus of Results and Discussion sections of 321 open access SLA articles. Firstly, raw frequency counts were calculated for ten concessive markers as indicated by Zhang (2021) and ten concordance lines per marker were randomly sampled for functional classification. Secondly, collocational profiles were created in AntConc v4.3.1 with a ± 5 -word window, a minimum frequency threshold of five, and log-likelihood ranking (Anthony, 2024). Results indicated that over 60 percent of the occurrences are made up of adversative and contrastive markers which serve the primary purpose of sentence and paragraph level transitions. In comparison, subordinating conjunctions and prepositional forms, although infrequent, are used for clause-level mitigation alongside broader discourse level concession. The results demonstrate the importance of frequency analysis alongside concordance-based classification and collocational profiling to articulate complex functional differences among concessive marker types. From a pedagogical perspective, the study indicates that teaching both the marker type and its typical cotextual framing using academic texts may improve coherence in the learners' writing.

Keywords: Academic Writing, Antconc, Concessive Markers, Corpus Linguistics, Second Language Acquisition

Introduction

In academic writing, precise articulation of claims and counterclaims is imperative. One of the distinguishing features of advanced academic writing is the use of concessive markers such as *although*, *even though*, *despite*, and *however*. These markers are important in signaling contrast, and enable writers to recognize limitations or other views while still holding onto their argumentative position (Hinkel, 2002; Zhang, 2021; Hyland, 2005). The results and discussion segments of scholarly publications are particularly abundant with concessive constructions because these sections incorporate the convergence of hypothesized and realized outcomes along with their negotiating constraints in context as well as gaps within existing research (Charles, 2006; Liu & Deng, 2020). Concessive markers hold significant value in these sections, but have received little to no attention in corpus approaches. The focus of prior studies has been either on the use of concessive markers in academic writing or on learner corpora without paying attention to the specific rhetorical parts of text (Zhang, 2021; Le Bruyn & Paquot, 2020).

The development of corpus-linguistic tools enables the systematic, large-scale study of these markers (Biber, Conrad & Reppen, 1998; Anthony, 2024). The more recent developments of corpus technologies, like AntCorGen, offer the ability to target specific excerpts from academic texts. This functionality enables scholars to

construct functionally tailored corpora that serve specific genre needs. This approach expands the scope of studying the functioning of concessive markers in the Results and Discussion sections of the academic texts, as their function in the expression of contrast, limitation and stance is very prominent (Anthony, 2024; Flowerdew, 2015).

Prior studies have focused on counting the markers and pay little attention to their discourse structure, meaning-based classification, or the rhetorical role they serve in the text (Hyland & Tse, 2005; Zhang, 2021). In addition, very few studies that consider quantitative corpus analysis with qualitative functional interpretation from the SFL perspective have been conducted (Martin & Rose, 2007; Ndoricimpa, 2019). Similarly, concessive markers have not been examined in the context of the Results and Discussion sections from a functional, corpus-based approach, even though they are pivotal to academic argumentation. To address these gaps, this study builds a specific corpus comprising Results and Discussion sections of Second Language Acquisition (SLA) using AntCorGen, and subsequently analyzes the concessive markers within this corpus using SFL and Zhang's (2021) approach. The objective is to uncover not only the markers that are used, but also the ways they function rhetorically to support claims, manage contrasts, and engage with the disciplinary norms. The study will be guided by the following research questions: 1. What are the frequencies of concessive markers outlined by Zhang (2021) in the Results and Discussion sections of SLA research articles? 2. What are the collocational profiles of these concessive markers, and how do these profiles shape the text's rhetorical framework?

This study contributes to the field of corpus linguistics, discourse analysis, and English for Academic Purposes (EAP) in various respects. First, it offers a comprehensive, functionally grounded description of concessive marker usage in a critical section of academic writing. Second, it illustrates the importance of integrating corpus-based approaches with SFL to uncover the underlying structure of academic writing. Third, the arguments put forward in this study may assist in developing the pedagogical framework for teaching advanced academic writing by enabling students and novice researchers to understand the structure of persuasive discourse and the role of concessive markers for constructing balanced arguments.

Literature Review

Concessive Markers in L2 Writing

Concessive markers- words like although, however, even though, and despite- play a crucial role in advancing layered argumentation. By deploying these terms, academic authors offset primary assertions, acknowledge weaker counterclaims, and announces contrasts that keep discourse persuasive. In learners second-language (L2) contexts the same terms often appear in a rigid manner that misses local conventions and pragmatic weight. Shifting from pedagogy to taxonomy. This gap apparently comes from linguistic limits, cognitive load, cultural habits, and the rhetorical choices each writer makes (Hinkel, 2002; Zhang, 2020). Ädel (2006) groups concession with hedging and stance markers under the broad umbrella of metadiscourse. On the other hand, Paltridge (1997) notes that many ESL thesis writers rely on these devices simply to meet disciplinary conventions.

Altenberg and Tapper (1998) explored the English essays of Swedish L2 writers

and found that concessive markers tended to appear in low frequency. The limited vocabulary, they argued, was compounded by L1 influence, which often relocated the markers to unusual positions in the sentence. Hinkel (2002) reported a different but related problem in the work of adult ESL students: a heavy reliance on a narrow cluster of familiar concessives at the expense of rarer and more formal options. Because of this repetition, many texts lose evaluative depth and variation. Similarly, the work of Mauranen (1993) on Finnish academic English also pointed out the existence of cross-cultural variation in concessive marker use as he postulated that L2 writers of English tend to borrow some rhetorical strategies from their mother tongues, thus making their writing pragmatically less suitable. The studies conducted by Mauranen (1993) and Ädel (2006) showcased how L2 students tend to transfer specific rhetorical patterns from their first language affecting their use of concessive markers. For instance, learners from Finland and China tend to underuse the markers although and nevertheless, which results in pragmatic inaccuracies. These results support the need for culturally appropriate writing instruction. Similarly, Jarrah (2021) deploys concession analysis grounded in corpus linguistics to examine Jordanian Arabic, revealing a distinctive pattern of typological variation alongside its pragmatic functions. Such findings carry practical weight for classroom instruction and for corpus-based scholarship alike, underscoring how cultural backdrop and linguistic choice together shape the meaning of concessive markers in non-Western settings.

Corpus-based research from the past few years has begun to substantiate, and in some cases refine, what earlier classroom observations reported. Zhang's (2020) investigation into Chinese EFL students use of adversative and concessive conjunctions revealed a striking pattern: certain markers were deployed far too often, others scarcely at all. This uneven distribution hints at an incomplete grasp of how such words actually shape sophisticated rhetorical moves. Blending corpus methods with rhetorical structure theory, she showed that misplaced concessive terms often negatively affected coherence and argumentation. The study, also informed by systemic functional linguistics, argued that researchers must track the meaning of a marker as closely as its raw frequency.

Semantic Function of Concessive Markers

Scholars have noted that concessive markers do more than simply signal opposition; they carry distinct shades of meaning that can be grouped under concession, contrast, or mitigation. Framing study around this semantic function invites scholars to look past raw occurrence statistics and track how the markers actively build the sense of a sentence (Zhang 2021; Halliday & Matthiessen 2014). For instance, although is often viewed as marking concession, and its counterpart however marks a shift toward contrastive discourse progression. Research carried out by Wiechmann and Kerz (2013) and Ndoricimpa (2019) demonstrates that reviewing the semantic function enables one to understand how the author breaks down their arguments and manages the stance more appropriately. In addition, they demonstrate the multifunctionality of some markers, which may assume different semantic functions depending on their syntactic position and co-text. This illustrates the necessity of qualitative analysis, even in large corpora.

Moreover, Taboada and Das (2013) analyzed discourse relations in scholarly texts and noted the significance of concessive markers in indicating coherence relations,

especially in argumentative texts. Most recently, Fraser (2009) created a detailed taxonomy of discourse markers where he placed concessives as a separate group and described them as markers that contribute toward the writer's position with respect to the text as well as the logical progression of ideas. These observations are important in the context of academic writing where brevity and clarity, as well as logical and precise argumentation, are essential.

Concessive markers have been investigated with regard to their usage across different academic fields. Hyland (2005) demonstrated that humanities scholars tend to use more concessive and contrastive markers than their counterparts in the sciences, which indicates different conventional rhetorical practices. Also, the use of concessive markers has been studied in relation to different academic disciplines. It was shown by Hyland (2005) that humanities scholars tend to use more concessive and contrastive markers than their science counterparts on account of differing customary conventions. In her study, Charles (2006) noted that citation practices tend to coincide with concessive structures, particularly in the literature review and discussion sections. In contemporary studies of language acquisition, scholars often introduce concessive markers to qualify particular results within ongoing theoretical debates. Despite this practical use, intensive corpus-driven analysis of those very markers in learner corpora is still sparse, indicating a noticeable gap in the field.

Corpus-Based Collocational Studies of Academic Concession

Recent studies employing corpus-assisted discourse analysis have demonstrated that close attention to collocation can reveal, at times quite sharply, the subtle functional distinctions among concessive markers in academic writing (Flowerdew, 2024). Independent corpus investigations carried out by graduate students have found that second-language authors sharpen their understanding of collocational patterns—such as concessive devices—by examining materials from naturally occurring settings (Hua et al., 2024). Complementary work on linking adverbials finds that first- and second-language authors default to different collocational patterns, a gap that points educators toward genre-sensitive instructional frameworks (Yue, 2024).

Diachronic studies on ELT publications illustrate the changing uses and frequencies of adversative and concessive conjunctions, indicating changes in the conventions of the field (Safari & Mahdavi, 2024). Zwayyer et al. (2024) have analyzed lexical bundles and the collocation of adjectives giving more insights into the evaluative and discursal functions that often accompany concessive markers. Corpus studies of the Italian students' writings from a cross-linguistic perspective demonstrate that adversative markers universally pivot discourse changes (Ferrato, 2024).

Concessive markers are gaining attention, but some gaps are yet to be explored. Firstly, specific disciplines such as research on language acquisition have largely been ignored because most works centered on learner corpora or broader academic writing genres. Secondly, the context within which concessive markers are used is often studied in isolation, and although many focus on the frequency of their use, fewer studies look at how these markers' meanings are constructed in relation to the context of their usage. Corpus linguistics provides adequate methods for identifying and analyzing the concessive markers in academic texts. Moreover,

tools such as AntConc and AntCorGen allow scholars to obtain concordance lines from particular sections, for example, results and discussion, and then analyze the contextual use of the markers (Anthony, 2024). Therefore, by using a corpus based approach, this study attempts to address these gaps by a conducting a semantic function analysis of concessive markers in the Results and Discussion sections of SLA research articles.

Methodology

Theoretical Orientation and Research Design

This study uses a corpus-based research design to analyze the rhetorical and semantic roles of concessive markers in academic texts. The study relies principally on qualitative analysis because it seeks to map the semantic role of concessive markers rather than to tally their occurrences. Data collection is confined to the Results and Discussion segments of research articles dealing with language acquisition. This selective focus was informed by a desire to observe how scholars deploy concessive forms for contrast, concession, and mitigation in their arguments (Zhang, 2021; Hyland, 2005).

The present study draws its theoretical underpinnings from Systemic Functional Linguistics, paying special attention to what Halliday and Matthiessen (2014) label the interpersonal metafunction. This facet of grammar attends to how utterances perform social duties, create roles, and sustain relationships, particularly through stance, evaluation, and engagement. Viewed through this lens, concessive markers appear as meaningful resources that allow authors to acknowledge alternatives while steering contrastive shifts in their argument. Moreover, those markers prove indispensable to the rhetorical coherence and persuasive discipline expected of academic discourse (Martin & Rose, 2007).

Data Collection

To address the study's focus and scope, a specialized corpus was constructed using AntCorGen (Anthony, 2022), which allows the extraction of specific sections from research articles and/or complete articles. The corpus composed for the study consists of the Results and Discussion sections from 321 peer-reviewed articles taken from journals in language acquisition. Together the papers contain 695,474 tokens and were published between 2010 and 2024. Articles were selected to cover a wide spread of topics within language acquisition, including second-language learning, bilingualism, and EFL pedagogy. The criteria set was intended to preserve focus and coherence: the scope of the study is limited to Results and Discussion sections of texts authored in English as delineated in the scope of work. Excluded from this selection are editorials, review articles, and theoretical works without accompanying empirical evidence. This approach to selection together with the defined criteria serves to enhance the representativeness and functionality of the corpus with regard to the study objectives (Biber et al., 1998).

Extraction and Data Sampling

The AntConc concordancer, designed for word-in-context analysis, served as the initial collection point for concessive markers. Given the overall size of the corpus and the volume of these markers, a random sample was drawn to keep the dataset manageable while remaining representative for qualitative probing. Copilot and

ChatGPT were then used to get ten randomly selected concordance lines per marker. Collocational profiles were then analyzed, built with AntConc version 4.3.1 after designating each target marker as the node word and setting the span at five words on either side (left and right). Associations were ranked by log-likelihood and mutual information scores, combining statistical weight with raw frequency. To reduce noise, only collocates with a frequency of at least five occurrences were retained. The final list was saved as CSV files to allow for subsequent merging and exploration. This step preserved the transparency and reproducibility of the entire process of data extraction and analysis.

Selection of Concessive Markers

The concession markers selected for the present analysis stem from their established rhetorical weight and their prominence in previous academic works (Zhang 2021; Hyland 2005; Halliday and Matthiessen 2014). Following Zhang's (2021) classification schema consisting of four types of concessive markers, a set of ten items was used. Three concessive terms-although, though, even though-belong to Type A, two contrastive expressions-despite and in spite of-are drawn from Type B, three adversative connectives-however, nevertheless, and nonetheless-adhere to Type C, and finally, Type D is represented by while and whereas. Such a balanced sampling allows researchers to study concession not only within individual clauses but also across the wider flow of discourse. The resulting classification scheme highlights the various ways that concessive markers help build meaning in expert academic conversation. Each concordance line was examined in its context and manually tagged according to the specific role it played in the given context. The rationale of using semantic function analysis instead of a purely syntactic or quantitative approach stems from the fact that concessive markers tend to serve more than one contextual rhetorical function within a given context (Wiechmann & Kerz, 2013; Ndoricimpa, 2019). This method is coherent with the broader objectives of the study which sought to reveal how language operates to formulate persuasive and contextually appropriate academic discourse. Moreover, the corpus comprises publicly available academic research articles so there was no issue of ethical considerations. In the course of the study, no personal or sensitive data was collected, and all sources were acknowledged appropriately according to scholarly conventions.

Results

Distribution and Functional Classification of Concessive Markers

In table 4.1, raw frequencies of ten target markers are displayed alongside their classification in Zhang's four-type system and primary rhetorical function against 321 journal articles' results and discussion sections with a total of 695,474 tokens.

Table 1 Raw frequencies with Zhang types and primary functions (N = 321)

Marker	Frequency	Primary Function	Zhang Type
although	350	Mitigating concession	Type A
even though	82	Mitigating concession	Type A
though	185	Mitigating concession	Type A
despite	151	Abstract concession	Type B

in spite of	9	Abstract concession	Type B
however	967	Discourse transition	Type C
nevertheless	85	Discourse transition	Type C
nonetheless	40	Discourse transition	Type C
while	729	Parallel contrast	Type D
whereas	235	Parallel contrast	Type D

The predominance of markers of Type C (e.g. however) and Type D (e.g. while, whereas) both of which account for more than 60% of all occurrences suggests that authors mainly use sentence or paragraph level tools to shape and direct reader attention. In comparison, Types A and B, consisting of subordinating conjunctions and prepositional terms respectively, tend to be infrequent but serve more defined specialized hedging functions by softer mitigation or abstract concession.

Collocational Profiles by Marker Type

As discussed in the methodology section (AntConc ± 5 -word window; raw frequency ≥ 5 ; range ≥ 5 documents), we compiled collocate lists, exported them as CSV files, and ordered collocates by log-likelihood. Discussed below are Tables 2–5, which showcase the top three collocates for one representative marker in each Zhang type along with some interpretive discussion.

Type A – *although*

(Mitigating concession) Table

2 Top collocates for *although*

Collocate	FreqLR	Range	LL-score
not	43	32	30.67
is	55	45	20.91
did	16	15	20.27

The strong connection with not immediately to the right of *although* verifies its function in clause-level mitigation (“*although not significant...*”). The high frequency of *is* shows a bias toward utilizing auxiliary-fronted forms (“*although it is possible...*”), which allows authors to hedge certain propositions while retaining coherence in the global argument structure. The presence of *did* suggests some form of methodological comment limitation (“*although we did control for...*”), supporting the general idea of how *although* governs the restriction of claims at the clause level.

Type B – *despite* (Abstract concession) Table 3 Top collocates for *despite*

Collocate	FreqLR	Range	LL-score
fact	11	9	44.26
being	8	8	22.99
their	23	15	20.03

The prevailing collocate *fact* arises from the stock phrase “*despite the fact that...*,” which allows for an abstract concession that qualifies all findings rather than individual clauses. The collocate *being* is found in participial constructions (e.g. “*despite being evident...*”), thus projecting the concession to more general propositions. Their as a pronoun frequently introduces concessions to prior work

(“despite their report...”), which emphasizes the role of despite as a discourse level qualifier.

Type C – *however* (Discourse transition) Table 4 Top collocates for *however*

Collocate	FreqLR	Range	LL-score
and	161	88	78.96
it	86	64	62.64
is	150	92	55.16

However mostly co-occurs with and, it, and is, which marks its main use as a sentence-initial pivot (“However It is clear...”; “However and notably...”). The remarkably high LL for and indicates strong coupling to additive constructions, confirming that Type C markers operate at the level of paragraph transitions and not at the level of propositions.

Type D – *while* (Parallel contrast) Table 5 Top collocates for *while*

Collocate	FreqLR	Range	LL-score
others	13	11	32.83
as	23	21	22.54
there	26	23	13.67

The collocate others is often used in phrases like “while others reported...,” demonstrating how while serves to create parallel contrasts between comparable propositions. Its occurrence with as and there co extends further support to its comparative clause setting function as opposed to a hedging role. Thus, Type D markers contribute to argumentative structure in an additive fashion by collocating ideas in close proximity.

The integrated collocational and distributional evidence provides stratified ordering of concession strategies used in the Results and Discussion sections of academic texts: Type A (Mitigation) occurs through clause-internal negation and auxiliary frames that allow precise hedging of singular claims. Type B (Abstract concession) raises qualifying assertions to the level of discourse, thus framing entire findings as constrained by broader limitations. Type C (Discourse transitions) manages intra-paragraph and inter-sentence transitions, leading the audience along sequenced arguments without substantially weakening information. Type D (Parallel contrast) posits two propositions in contention with one another, exercising a syntactic contrastive function instead of mitigating. Thus these observations indicate that specific classes of markers are selected to serve distinct rhetorical functions such as fine mitigation or macro level discourse management showing that writers do not treat concessive markers as synonyms.

Discussion

This study sheds light on the use of concessive markers in SLA academic writing and argues that such markers are used systematically based on rhetorical reasoning. The choices made are influenced by genre, discourse position, and the intended communicative purpose. The dominance of Type C and Type D markers, especially *however* and *while*, supports the hypothesis that SLA researchers prioritize discourse-level transitions in comparison to clause-level mitigations. This is not a random occurrence. It corroborates Halliday and Hasan's (1976) claim regarding the use of adversative conjunctions for cohesion in texts and endorses Paltridge's (1997) argument that genre conventions dictate the placement of discourse markers in academic prose. In this context, the reliance on contrastive and adversative transitions is transformed from a stylistic choice to an essential rhetorical mandate. Concentrating on mere frequency would be oversimplifying the use of concessive markers. This study delves deeper by illustrating that the semantic function and collocational behavior of concessive markers need to be analyzed together in order to appreciate

their contribution to meaning construction. For instance, *although* and *though* often collocate with negation (*not*) and auxiliary verbs (*is*, *did*), allowing for clause-internal hedging. This is consistent with Ädel's (2006) taxonomy of metadiscourse and with Ndoricimpa's (2019) critique which posits that concessive relations are vital in nuanced stance-shifting. Most importantly, purely quantitative approaches have unnoticed this sophisticated behavior, which is a gap this research aimed to fill.

More recent research Zhang (2020, 2021) focused on the misuse and overuse of concessive markers by L2 learners, showing that the learners' arguments became less clear. However, these studies treated the markers as they appear in broader academic writing, overlooking genre-specific parts like the Results and Discussion sections. This study addresses this gap by explaining how concessive markers are used to claim, counterclaim, acknowledge, and respond to limitations, rebut evidence, or otherwise engage in critical discourse, which are important dimensions in interpreting empirical evidence. Moreover, the results contribute not only descriptively but also functionally support Zhang's (2021) typological model. Consider the case of high log-likelihood collocates like *despite* (e.g., *fact*, *being*); they reflect a rhetorical technique known as abstract concession, which prioritizes the broader implications or limitations of the study rather than the straightforward result. This functional distribution supports Halliday and Matthiessen's (2014) conception of interpersonal metafunction of language, defining language as a resource for enacting social relationships and evaluative stance. Authors exercise these roles in the Results and Discussion chapters by modulating claims, evaluating relevance, and interacting with audience from the discipline. With the application of systemic functional theory and collocation analysis, this study justifies empirically what has been taken for granted: the assumption that concessive markers are the driving force of academic discourse and disagreement. Furthermore, the techniques utilized, AntConc for collocational profiling, respond directly to calls by Biber et al. (1998) and Anthony (2022, 2024) for transparent and reproducible corpus methods. This study goes beyond earlier works that relied on intuition or singular examples; it systematically identifies

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patterns within a large, functionally specific corpus. The five-word window, defined frequency thresholds, and line-by-line analysis of concordance results establish a baseline that enhances methodological rigor in discourse research assisted by corpus linguistics.

Lastly, this study emphasizes the need to shift focus in the instruction of academic writing and addresses pedagogical concerns. As noted by Hyland (2005), effective academic writing relies greatly on the author's management of stance as well as the ability to consider counter arguments. The present findings demonstrate that these rhetorical moves are not solely the result of word choices; rather, they are the outcome of a structured, collocationally primed systems. Thus, empowering L2 writers with pattern recognition, especially the precise use of *although*, *despite*, *however*, and *while*, can vastly enhance their ability to craft cohesive and persuasive academic texts. This is aligned with the pedagogical concerns put forth by Hinkel (2002) and Martin and Rose (2007) who advocated for instruction based on particular genres centered on authentic discourse frameworks. To conclude, this study moves beyond mere counts of concessive markers and advances a multi-layered, functional explanation of their use in SLA R&D discourse. It shows that concessive markers are not interchangeable; rather, they are systematically patterned and strategically used to navigate contrasts, hedge claims, and guide the academic argumentative discourse. These findings have both theoretical significance for the genre and discourse analysis, and practical significance for teaching academic writing.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that there are four clear types of English concessive markers in the Results and Discussion sections of the texts as highlighted by Zhang (2021). The markers *however* and *while* (Types C and D) constitute over 60% of all occurrences and serve primarily as sentence or paragraph-level transitions. Less frequent subordinators such as *although* and *though* (Type A) and prepositional forms like *despite* (Type B) perform sharper clause-level hedging strategies and soften individual clauses or qualify whole arguments. The collocational patterns, like the strong “*although + not*” frame or the fixed “*however + and*” pivot, show that these devices have become conventional templates in academic writing.

Further research may focus on comparing concessive strategies across different STEM and humanities or adding sections like Methods and Introduction, as well as tracking the diachronic development of marker use. In addition, learner-corpus studies would demonstrate how writers assimilate these patterns, and the integration of semantic prosody measurement or multi-word clustering would provide additional insight into stance and evaluation. From a practical perspective, the derived conclusions can be used to enhance teaching English for Academic Purposes, as they go beyond the pinpointed markers to frame context-relevant co-occurrences of these devices, thus enabling students to express ideas with clarity and nuance.

This study has some limitations, even with its contributions. It is based on open-access articles which may over-represent certain disciplines, and it does not consider markers with fewer than five occurrences, which could result in missing recently developed or stylistically marked uses. Additionally, the sole

use of log-likelihood for collocate ranking may bias the results toward high-frequency patterns and overlook infrequent but significant ones. In future research, these concerns could be investigated by expanding the corpus sample, lowering the frequency thresholds, and employing a broader set of statistical criteria.

References

- Ädel, A. (2006). *Metadiscourse in L1 and L2 English*. John Benjamins.
- Altenberg, B., & Tapper, M. (1998). The use of adverbial connectors in advanced Swedish learners' written English. In S. Granger (Ed.), *Learner English on computer* (pp. 80–93). Longman.
- Anthony, L. (2024). *AntConc* (Version 4.3.1) [Computer software]. Tokyo, Japan: Waseda University. <https://www.laurenceanthony.net/software/antconc/>
- Anthony, L. (2022). *AntCorGen* (Version 1.2.0) [Computer software]. Tokyo, Japan: Waseda University. <https://www.laurenceanthony.net/software/antcorgen/>
- Biber, D., Conrad, S., & Reppen, R. (1998). *Corpus linguistics: Investigating language structure and use*. Cambridge University Press.
- Biber, D., & Gray, B. (2010). Challenging stereotypes about academic writing: Complexity, elaboration, explicitness. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 9(1), 2–20.
- Charles, M. (2006). Phraseological patterns in reporting clauses used in citation: A corpus-based study of theses in two disciplines. *English for Specific Purposes*, 25(3), 310–331.
- Flowerdew, J. (2015). Corpus-based research and pedagogy in EAP: From lexis to genre. *Language Teaching*, 48(2), 153–173.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Hasan, R. (1976). *Cohesion in English*. Longman.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Matthiessen, C. M. I. M. (2014). *Halliday's introduction to functional grammar* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- Hinkel, E. (2002). *Second language writers' text: Linguistic and rhetorical features*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Hyland, K. (2005). *Metadiscourse: Exploring interaction in writing*. Continuum.
- Hyland, K., & Tse, P. (2005). Hooking the reader: A corpus study of evaluative “that” in abstracts. *English for Specific Purposes*, 24(2), 123–139.
- Jarrah, M., Alghazo, S., & Bader, Y. (2021). Two types of concession: Evidence from discourse markers. *SAGE Open*, 11(3), 1–13.
- Le Bruyn, B., & Paquot, M. (2020). The functions of lexical bundles across L1 and L2 writing. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, 25(2), 183–210.
- Liu, Y., & Deng, L. (2020). A corpus-based study of stance markers in English academic writing. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 45, 100857.
- Martin, J. R., & Rose, D. (2007). *Working with discourse: Meaning beyond the clause* (2nd ed.). Continuum.
- Mauranen, A. (1993). *Cultural differences in academic rhetoric: A textlinguistic study*. Peter Lang.
- Ndoricimpa, A. (2019). A corpus-based study of concessive relations in academic writing. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 8(1), 1–10.
- Paltridge, B. (1997). Thesis and dissertation writing: Preparing ESL students for research. *English for Specific Purposes*, 16(1), 61–70.
- Taboada, M., & Das, D. (2013). Annotation upon annotation: Adding signalling

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information to a corpus of discourse relations. *Dialogue & Discourse*, 4(2), 249–281.

Wiechmann, D., & Kerz, E. (2013). Semantic association and the directionality of argument structure alternations: A distributional semantics approach. *Corpus Linguistics and Linguistic Theory*, 9(2), 251–288.

Zhang, M. (2020). The use of adversative and concessive conjunctions in Chinese EFL learners' writing. *System*, 88, 102183.

Zhang, M. (2021). *Concessive relations in learner writing: A corpus-based study*. Springer.